

PRIVACY-PRESERVING MULTI-KEYWORD SEARCH IN INFORMATION NETWORK

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Abstract:

Objective- In emerging information networks, it is crucially important to provide efficient search on distributed documents while preserving their owners privacy, for which privacy preserving indexes or PPI presents a possible solution. An understudied problem for the PPI techniques is how to provide differentiated privacy preservation in the presence of multi-keyword document search.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- To develop a web server which is the main server used, then there is a database for storing the Key-word in the encrypted format and finally to provide the distributed document search with quantitatively differentiated privacy preservation.

Findings- It consist of three sections. First main step is the multi-keyword generation. The client data is modified by eliminating common words by selecting specific words. The keywords are encrypted with public key and shows in database. When the third party searches data with a multi-keyword. The multi-keyword is encrypted and it is searched in database. If it is matched during comparison then the search will be success, but if the search is success then also it will not retrieve data. It only notifies the data is present. It maintains the privacy by using clients own private key. The data only decrypted by client with its own private key.

Limitations- Search process is efficient, but it takes time to search the document and it has to be taken into consideration.

Practical implications- This paper is very helpful for those who require their data to be kept in more privacy and it can be search efficiently.

Originality/Value- This will help in improving the efficiency of the searching process by maintaining reliability in data storage of client.

Keywords- Privacy, information networks, secure multi-party computations, indexing

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

With the development of cloud computing and popularization of mobile web, cloud online services are becoming more useful for people's life. People are requested to submit their personal information to the cloud by the internet. When people do this, they hope the service provider will provide security to protect their data from leaking,

so other people will not invade their privacy. With more and more services and applications are emerging in the internet, it becomes easier to expose the user's sensitive data in the internet. Without much attention to this problem, it will result in the break out of leaking messages. The shared data in cloud servers, however, usually contains users' sensitive information (e.g., personal profile, financial data, health records, etc.) and needs to be well protected. One of the most important reasons for exposing sensitive user data is that the user data will be stored in the cloud environment for a long time, which may not be controlled by the user himself. As the ownership of the data is separated from the administration of them, the cloud servers may migrate users' data to other cloud servers in outsourcing or share them in cloud searching. Therefore, it becomes a big challenge to protect the privacy of those shared data in cloud, especially in cross-cloud and big data environment. These are the major challenges to protect people's privacy. Self-destructing data systems are designed to address these concerns. Their goal is to destroy data after a pre-specified timeout. In order to meet this challenge, it is necessary to design a comprehensive solution to support user-defined authorization period and to provide fine-grained access control during this period. The shared data should be self-destroyed after the user-defined expiration time will increases the security for shared data's in cloud.

1.1.1 Comparison of Privacy Preserving Single-Keyword Search and Multi-Keyword Ranked Search Techniques over Encrypted Cloud Data

Cloud computing otherwise known as on demand computing. It provides the services over the internet. It has the provision of facilitating users to store and access their data in and from cloud server by sitting anywhere and on any device. Storing data in cloud server also opens up so many security threats as data is accessed over internet and client has no direct control over data once uploaded into cloud server. We first implement a basic idea for the Single Keyword Search Over Encrypted Data And then Multi-keyword Ranked. Search over Encrypted cloud data (MRSE) based on secure inner product computation and efficient similarity measure of coordinate matching, i.e., as many matches as possible, in order to capture the relevance of data documents to the search query, then we give two significantly improved MRSE schemes to achieve various stringent privacy requirements in two different threat models. Assignment of anonymous ID to the user to provide more security to the data on cloud server is done. To improve the search experience of the data search service, further extension of the two schemes to support more Search semantics is done.

1.1.2 Privacy-Preserving Multi-keyword Ranked Search over Encrypted Cloud Data

With the advent of cloud computing, data owners are motivated to outsource their complex data management systems from local sites to the commercial public cloud for great flexibility and economic savings. But for protecting data privacy, sensitive data has to be encrypted before outsourcing, which obsoletes traditional data utilization based on plaintext keyword search. Thus, enabling an encrypted cloud data search service is of paramount importance. Considering the large number of data users and documents in the cloud, it is necessary to allow multiple keywords in the search request and return documents in the order of their relevance to these keywords. Related

works on searchable encryption focus on single keyword search or Boolean keyword search, and rarely sort the search results. In this paper, for the first time, we define and solve the challenging problem of privacy preserving multi-keyword ranked search over encrypted cloud data (MRSE). We establish a set of strict privacy requirements for such a secure cloud data utilization system. Among various multi keyword semantics, we choose the efficient similarity measure of “coordinate matching”, i.e., as many matches as possible, to capture the relevance of data documents to the search query. We further use “inner product similarity” to quantitatively evaluate such similarity measure. We first propose a basic idea for the MRSE based on secure inner product computation, and then give two significantly improved MRSE schemes to achieve various stringent privacy requirements in two different threat models. Thorough analysis investigating privacy and efficiency guarantees of proposed schemes is given. Experiments on the real-world dataset further proposed schemes indeed introduce low overhead on computation and communication.

1.1.3 An Efficient and Privacy-Preserving Semantic Multi-Keyword Ranked Search over Encrypted Cloud Data

As so much advantage of cloud computing, more and more data owners centralize their sensitive data into the cloud. With a mass of data files stored in the cloud server, it is important to provide keyword based search service to data user. However, in order to protect the data privacy, sensitive data is usually encrypted before outsourced to the cloud server, which makes the search technologies on plain text unusable. In this paper, we propose a semantic multi-keyword ranked search scheme over the encrypted cloud data, which simultaneously meets a set of strict privacy requirements. Firstly, we utilize the “Latent Semantic Analysis” to reveal relationship between terms and documents. The latent semantic analysis takes advantage of implicit higher-order structure in the association of terms with documents (“semantic structure”) and adopts a reduced-dimension vector space to represent words and documents. Thus, the relationship between terms is automatically captured. Secondly, our scheme employ secure “k-nearest neighbor (k-NN)” to achieve secure search functionality. The proposed scheme could return not only the exact matching files, but also the files including the terms latent semantically associated to the query keyword. Finally, the experimental result demonstrates that our method is better than the original MRSE scheme.

1.1.4 Privacy Preserving Multi-Keyword Ranked Search with Anonymous ID Assignment over Encrypted Cloud Data

The advancement in cloud computing has motivated the data owners to outsource their data management systems from local sites to commercial public cloud for great flexibility and economic savings. But people can enjoy full benefit of cloud computing if we are able to address very real privacy and security concerns that come with storing sensitive personal information. For real privacy, user identity should remain hidden from CSP (Cloud service provider) and to protect privacy of data, data which is sensitive is to be encrypted before outsourcing. Thus, enabling an encrypted cloud data search service is of great importance. By considering the large number of data users, documents in the cloud, it is important for the search service to allow multi keyword query and provide result similarity ranking to meet the effective need of data retrieval search and not often differentiate the search results. In this system, we define and solve the challenging problem of privacy-preserving multi keyword ranked search over

encrypted cloud data (MRSE), and establish a set of strict privacy requirements for such a secure cloud data utilization system to be implemented in real. We first propose a basic idea for the Multi-keyword Ranked Search over Encrypted cloud data (MRSE) based on secure inner product computation and efficient similarity measure of coordinate matching, i.e., as many matches as possible, in order to capture the relevance of data documents to the search query, then we give two significantly improved MRSE schemes to achieve various stringent privacy requirements in two different threat models. Assignment of anonymous ID to the user to provide more security to the data on cloud server is done. To improve the search experience of the data search service, further extension of the two schemes to support more search semantics is done. The previous work mainly focused on providing privacy to the data on cloud in which using multi-keyword ranked search was provided over encrypted cloud data using efficient similarity measure of co-ordinate matching. The previous work also proposed a basic idea of MRSE using secure inner product computation. There was a need to provide more real privacy which this paper presents. In this system, stringent privacy is provided by assigning the cloud user a unique ID. This user ID is kept hidden from the cloud service provider as well as the third party user in order to protect the user's data on cloud from the CSP and the third party user. Thus, by hiding the user's identity, the confidentiality of user's data is maintained.

II. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

In the existing system, there is no full life cycle privacy security for data searching through cloud services. As the ownership of the data is separated from the administration of the data owner the cloud servers may migrate users data to other cloud servers in outsourcing or share them in cloud searching. In existing system we can search using a single keyword only. We cannot search the data in encrypted format and there it have less privacy compared to our propped system.

DISADVANTAGES

- Low efficiency.
- Time consuming.
- Privacy leakage.
- Low performance

2.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

Every user who is experienced in the existing system may think of a system that may add more flexibility. This work is designed in such a way to avoid the disadvantages of the existing system. The proposed system supports more elasticity, comfort capacity and safety.

The proposed idea is that a key policy attribute based encryption with time specified attributes (KP-TSABE) introduced. In this policy, every cipher text is labeled with a time interval while private key is associated with time instant. The cipher text can only be decrypted if both the time instant is in the allowed time interval and the attributes associated with the cipher text satisfy the key's access structure. The data will be securely self-destructed after a user specified expiration time.

ADVANTAGES

The proposed system achieves excellent performance in different prospects.

- Authentication and authorization
- Maximum Privacy
- Confidentiality, integrity, availability
- User defined data expiration time.
- Time based self destruction of data
- Multi tenancy, loss of control is limited.
- User friendly

III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION MODELS

3.1 IMPLEMENTATION MODULES

There are 3 modules in our Privacy-Preserving Multi-Keyword Search in Information Networks.

1. Indexer Module
2. Client Module
3. Encryption module

3.1.1 Indexer Module:

The main function of the module is to collect the data send by the clients to indexer and save it. The search queries are also provided to indexer. So the indexer has to search the encrypted data and get the result along with false positives.

3.1.2 Client Module:

The client machine is the machine in which the documents are created the main functions of the client is to create the document. Encrypt the document and send it to the indexer in the encrypted format. The encryption is done by encryption module.

3.1.3 Encryption Module:

In this module, the data owners should be able to upload the files. The files are encrypted before the files are uploaded to the cloud. The data owners are provided an option to enter the keywords for the file that are

uploaded to the server. These keywords are used for the indexing purpose which helps the search return values very quickly.

3.2. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

This figure shows the architecture diagram. It consist of three sections. First main step is the multi-keyword generation. The client data is modified by eliminating common words by selecting specific words. The keywords are encrypted with public key and shows in database. When the third party searches data with a multi-keyword. The multi-keyword is encrypted and it is searched in database. If it is matched during comparison then the search will be success, but if the search is success then also it will not retrieve data. It only notifies the data is present. It maintains the privacy by using clients own private key. The data only decrypted by client with its own private key.

Fig :
Architectur
e diagram

IV.CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose ϵ -MPPI for multi-term phrase publication with quantitative privacy control in emerging information networks. We propose several practical approaches for the secure construction of an ϵ -MPPI system in an environment without mutual trusts, while being able to provide the multi-term privacy. For practical performance of secure computations, we propose an MPC-reduction technique based on the efficient use of secret sharing schemes. We also discovered a common-term vulnerability and proposed a term-mixing solution. Through both simulation-based and real experiments, we show the advantage of ϵ -MPPI in terms of privacy preservation quality and construction efficiency.

In emerging information networks, it is crucially important to provide efficient search on distributed documents while preserving their owners' privacy, for which privacy preserving indexes or PPI presents a possible solution. An understudied problem for the PPI techniques is how to provide differentiated privacy preservation in the presence of multi-keyword document search. The differentiation is necessary as terms and phrases bear innate differences in their semantic meanings.

We also addressed the challenging problem of secure \mathcal{E} -MPPI construction in the multi-domain information network which lacks mutual trusts between domains. Towards a secure \mathcal{E} -MPPI construction with practically acceptable performance, we proposed to optimize the performance of secure multi-party computations by making a novel use of secret sharing. We implemented the \mathcal{E} -MPPI construction protocol with a functioning prototype. We conducted extensive experiments to evaluate the prototype's effectiveness and efficiency based on a real-world dataset.

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